

Formation Constants of Some Tl(I)-Halogen Substituted Salicylates and Effect of Halogen Atom on the Stability

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Formation constants of Tl(I) complexes with 5-chloro, 5-bromo and 5-iodo substituted salicylic acid were found to be in the order of Tl(I)-5ClSA > Tl(I)-5BrSA > Tl(I)-5ISA, where as protonation constants (Basicity) are in the order of 5ISA > 5BrSA > 5ClSA. This may be attributed to the steric effect of different halogen atoms in each case.

SURVEY of literature reveals that no work has been done on complexing tendencies of Tl(I) with 5-halogen substituted salicylic acid. In continuation of the previous work on the effect of nitro group on the formation constants of Tl(I)-salicylate complexes¹⁻³, present investigation deals with the effect of halogen atoms on the formation constants of Tl(I)-salicylates. Formation constants of Tl(I)-5-halogen substituted salicylates viz. 5-chloro salicylates [Tl(I)5CLSA], 5-bromo salicylates [Tl(I)5BrSA], and 5-iodo salicylates [Tl(I)5ISA] have been determined at 30°, using different computational methods viz. half-integral (HI), linear plot (LP) and point-wise calculation (PC) methods. Refined values are obtained by the method of least-squares (LS). Proton ligand formation constants required for the purpose, are also determined under the same experimental conditions using the aforesaid methods.

To study the effect of the halogen atom on the protonation and formation constants of Tl(I)-salicylates, proton ligand formation constants and formation constants of salicylic acid (SA) with Tl(I), have also been determined under the same experimental conditions and already reported⁶.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. Analar grade. Polymetron model CL-41 pH-meter was used for pH-metric titrations conducted at 30°. Measurements were made with an accuracy of ± 0.05 pH units and the reproducibility of the readings was of the same order.

pH-metric titrations of solution (i) free HClO_4 , (ii) free HClO_4 + ligand and (iii) free HClO_4 + ligand + Tl(I), were performed in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium against standard NaOH solution while maintaining the ionic strength at 0.1 M NaClO_4 .

The experimental set up and the method of calculation is the same as described earlier.

Proton ligand formation constants and formation constants of complexes :

The Irving-Rossotti expression⁴ was used for the calculation of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and $p(L)$. In the calculation of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and $p(L)$, the concentrations were corrected for the changes in volume as a result of addition of alkali during titrations. A series of values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and $p(L)$ corresponding to different B-values (pH meter readings) were calculated and the formation curves for the ligands and the complexes were obtained by plotting \bar{n}_A vs pH (B-value) and \bar{n} vs $p(L)$ respectively. The values of $\log K_n^H$, $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ for each case were recorded directly from the respective formation curve by half integral method. The values of pH (B-values) at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ and 1.5 correspond to values of $\log K_1^H$, and $\log K_2^H$ respectively, where as values of $p(L)$ at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 correspond to $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ respectively. Proton ligand formation constants and formation constants of complexes are calculated by linear plot and point-wise calculation method using equation :

$$\log K_n^H = B + \log \frac{\bar{n}_A - (n-1)}{n - \bar{n}_A}$$

and

$$\log K_n = p(L) + \log \frac{\bar{n} - (n-1)}{n - \bar{n}}$$

$$\left(\text{as } \log K_n = p(L)_{n - \frac{1}{2}} \right)^5$$

in the two regions where \bar{n}_A or \bar{n} is >1 and <1 .

Refined values of formation constants are obtained by the method of least squares. Values are recorded in Table-1, 2 and 3.

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TABLE-1

Tl(I)-5-CISA					Tl(I)-5-BrSA					Tl(I)-5-ISA				
B	\bar{n}	p(L)	Point-wise		B	\bar{n}	p(L)	Point-wise		B	\bar{n}	p(L)	Point-wise	
			$\log \bar{n}/(1-\bar{n}) \log K_1$					$\log \bar{n}/(1-\bar{n}) \log K_1$					$\log \bar{n}/(1-\bar{n}) \log K_1$	
6.0	0.353	9.08	-0.26	8.81	6.2	0.336	8.85	-0.30	8.55	6.6	0.372	8.44	-0.23	8.21
6.2	0.425	8.84	-0.13	8.71	6.4	0.388	8.60	-0.20	8.50	6.8	0.444	8.21	-0.10	8.11
6.4	0.504	8.57	+0.01	8.58	6.6	0.441	8.38	-0.10	8.28	7.0	0.536	7.97	-0.06	8.03
7.0	0.703	7.88	+0.37	8.25	7.0	0.578	7.90	+0.14	8.04	7.2	0.611	6.74	+0.20	7.93
7.6	0.852	7.12	+0.76	7.88	7.2	0.664	7.67	+0.30	7.97	7.4	0.682	7.49	+0.33	7.82
8.0	1.001	6.75	$\log(\bar{n}-1)/(2-\bar{n}) \log K_2$		8.0	1.020	6.72	$\log(\bar{n}-1)/(2-\bar{n}) \log K_2$		8.2	0.955	6.56	$\log(\bar{n}-1)/(2-\bar{n}) \log K_2$	
8.4	1.155	6.22	-0.74	5.48	9.0	1.323	5.56	-0.32	5.24	8.8	1.171	5.85	-0.69	5.17
8.6	1.203	5.99	-0.59	5.40	9.2	1.466	5.33	-0.06	5.28	9.0	1.259	5.62	-0.46	5.16
8.8	1.302	5.76	-0.36	5.39	9.4	1.550	5.09	+0.09	5.18	9.2	1.354	5.29	-0.26	5.02
9.2	1.442	5.29	-0.10	5.18	9.6	1.693	4.88	+0.35	5.23	9.4	1.433	5.14	-0.12	5.02
9.4	1.563	5.04	+0.11	5.15	9.8	1.824	4.66	+0.67	5.33	9.8	1.636	4.69	+0.24	4.93

TABLE-2 PROTON LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS

Method	5-CISA			5-BrSA			5-ISA			SA ^c		
	$\log K_1^H$	$\log K_2^H$	$\log K_B^H$	$\log K_1^H$	$\log K_2^H$	$\log K_B^H$	$\log K_1^H$	$\log K_2^H$	$\log K_B^H$	$\log K_1^H$	$\log K_2^H$	$\log K_B^H$
HI*	11.38	2.56	13.94	11.83	2.68	14.51	11.55	3.00	14.55	11.40	3.21	14.61
LP	11.58	2.60	14.18	11.51	2.66	14.17	11.76	2.99	14.75	12.00	3.20	15.20
PC	11.88	2.70	14.58	11.60	2.67	14.27	11.76	3.00	14.76	12.29	3.20	15.45
Average	11.61	2.62	14.23	11.65	2.67	14.32	11.69	3.00	14.69	11.90	3.20	15.10

*Values of $\log K_1^H$ are calculated from $\log K_B^H$

TABLE-3 FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Tl(I)-COMPLEXES

Method	Tl(I)-5-CISA			Tl(I)-5-BrSA			Tl(I)-5-ISA			Tl(I)-SA ^c		
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_B$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_B$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_B$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_B$
HI	8.55	5.15	13.70	8.28	5.20	13.48	8.00	5.00	13.00	8.95	5.00	13.95
LP	8.55	5.20	13.75	8.21	5.14	13.35	8.04	5.06	13.10	8.95	5.02	13.97
PC	8.45	5.32	13.77	8.27	5.25	13.52	8.02	5.04	13.06	8.75	5.07	13.82
LS	8.50	5.26	13.76	8.29	5.24	13.53	8.02	5.03	13.05	8.94	5.12	14.06
Average	8.51	5.23	13.74	8.26	5.21	13.47	8.02	5.03	13.05	8.90	5.05	13.95

Results and Discussion

Values of $\log K_1^H$, $\log K_2^H$ and $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ of 5-halogen substituted salicylic acid and their complexes with Tl(I), are recorded in Table 2 and 3.

The ratio of $\log K_1/K_2$ is positive in all the cases. A bigger difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ is because of possible steric hindrance on the linking of the second ligand molecule.

In view of very low concentration ($1 \times 10^{-4} M$) of Tl(I) used in the titration, formation of polynuclear

complexes may be ignored. Titrations performed using different ratios of metal to ligand, showed that the stability constants are independent of metal ion concentration in all the cases.

In all the cases \bar{n} value never exceeds 1.85, indicating thereby formation of only 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. Estimation of elements in the complexes isolated, also indicate 1 : 2 ratio of metal to ligand in all the cases.

Effect of halogen atom :

The order of K_1^H of the ligands used in the present investigation (Table-2) is :

SA > 5-ISA ≈ 5-BrSA ≈ 5-CISA
 and that of $\log K_{12}^H$ is :
 SA > 5-ISA > 5-BrSA > 5-CISA

where $\log K_1^H$ represents protonation of phenoxide group and $\log K_2^H$ protonation of carboxylate group. The order is in agreement with the order of inductive effect and resonance effect of the halogen atoms in each case⁷.

The order of overall basicity ($\log K_B^H$) is :
 SA > 5-ISA > 5-BrSA > 5-CISA

The order of formation constants of Tl(I)-complexes (Table-3) is :
 Tl(I)-SA > Tl(I)-5-CISA > Tl(I)-5-BrSA > Tl(I)-5-ISA

The order is not similar to the order of basicity of ligands but is similar to the order of the size of the halogen atoms :

I > Br > Cl

Hence this may be attributed to the steric hindrance of the halogen atoms⁸, which is expected for Tl(I) ion because of its bigger size in comparison to proton of very small size.

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